

EFFECT OF UNSTEADY FLOW WITH UNKNOWN FREQUENCIES ON BLADE STALL FLUTTER PREDICTION USING THE HARMONIC BALANCE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an investigation of the aeroelastic stability of a two-dimensional cascade (Standard Configuration 10) at large inflow angles. As the inflow angle increases, flow separation appears, which hinders the convergence of the harmonic balance solution. To assess the effect of flow separation on blade stall flutter prediction, a time-domain time marching method was applied to reveal that the dominant frequency of flow separation when the blade was stationary. This frequency was subsequently incorporated into the harmonic balance solution during flutter analysis, leading to a fully converged harmonic balance solution. A time-domain flutter analysis reveals that the flow field contains not only the blade vibration frequency f_2 and the flow separation frequency nf_1 ($n = 1, 2, 3$), but also scattered frequencies, such as $nf_2 \pm f_1$. These findings suggest that scattered frequencies be resolved for accurate stall flutter predictions using the harmonic balance method. Finally, based on the numerical setup described above, the aeroelastic stability of the cascade at large inflow angles was analyzed. The results demonstrate that the flow separation has a destabilizing effect on the blade aeroelasticity.

Keywords: Stall flutter, harmonic balance method, time-

domain method, flow separation

NOMENCLATURE

Q	conservative variable vector
V	volume of a cell
N	Number of harmonics
τ	pseudo time
f	frequency
β	inflow angle
p	unsteady pressure
k	reduced frequency

1 INTRODUCTION

Turbomachinery blade flutter is a critical aeroelastic instability. It can induce severe blade vibrations that may ultimately result in structural failure. It typically arises under off-design operating conditions, such as stall and choke. Among various types of flutter, stall flutter is particularly prevalent and hazardous. It occurs in the operating range between a working line and the stall boundary, thereby creating the so-called "flutter bite" [1]. Therefore, accurate prediction of stall flutter boundaries is es-

sential for ensuring aeroelastic stability, maintaining sufficient safety margins, and guaranteeing the durability of modern fans and compressors.

Stall flutter is classified into subsonic flutter and supersonic flutter by Mikolajczak et al. [2]. Subsonic stall flutter typically occurs near the stall boundary of part speeds. It is commonly associated with relatively large incidences of the flow. Under such circumstances, flow separation on a blade’s suction surface will arise. It is generally suspected that stall flutter is closely linked to flow separation. Buffum et al. [3] experimentally investigated the unsteady flow at large incidences in a linear oscillating cascade and demonstrated that separated flow exerts a strongly destabilizing influence on flutter, whereas attached flow has a stabilizing effect. Petrie-Repar et al. [4] conducted three-dimensional viscous flutter analysis for the Standard Configuration 10 (STCF10) blade, and found that significant flow blockage due to corner separation at the hub on the suction surface has a destabilizing effect on flutter. The aerodynamic damping of a two-dimensional cascade (STCF10) for various inlet flow angles and inlet Mach number was calculated by Petrie-Repar et al. [5]. Significant negative dampings were predicted for some off-design operating conditions where flow separation occurred. Vahdati et al. [6] reported that the shock has a stabilizing effect whereas the separation area behind it has a destabilizing effect. These studies collectively highlight that flow separation plays a pivotal role in stall flutter and must be accounted for in aeroelastic analysis.

In flutter analysis, it is crucial to accurately capture the unsteady flow induced by blade vibration. There are two primary strategies for obtaining unsteady flow: the traveling-wave method [7] and the influence coefficient method [8, 9]. Regardless of the approach, solving the three-dimensional unsteady Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes (UFANS) equations is required. These equations can be integrated either in the time domain using the dual time-stepping method [10], or in the frequency domain using methods such as the linear harmonic method [11], the nonlinear harmonic method [12], or the time-domain harmonic balance method [13]. Compared with time-domain methods, frequency-domain approaches offer higher computational efficiency but require prior knowledge of the unsteady flow frequencies. In the context of flutter analysis, blade vibration frequencies can typically be obtained in advance through modal analysis. As a result, frequency-domain methods—such as the harmonic balance method—have been widely used in flutter analysis of fan and compressor blades [14].

However, near the stall point, unsteady phenomena such as tip leakage flow and boundary layer separation occur with frequencies that are not known *a priori*. These unknown frequencies present major challenges for solving the harmonic balance equations, since the method requires the unsteady frequencies as input. Kielb et al. [15] observed oscillations in the residual of the steady solution for flow over a two-dimensional compressor blade. It indicated the presence of potential physical insta-

bilities such as boundary-layer separation. They subsequently computed the unsteady flow using the harmonic balance method with several assumed fundamental frequencies. Convergence was achieved only near 1265 Hz, whereas the residual variations remained relatively flat across other frequency ranges. McMullen et al. [16] proposed a gradient-based variable time-period (GBVTP) method to resolve unknown frequencies in the flow field and successfully computed the Strouhal vortex-shedding frequency of flow around a cylinder at low Reynolds numbers. One potential problem with the GBVTP method is that the residual is a weak function of frequency except very close to the correct unknown frequency [17]. Moreover, in stall flutter analysis, not only the flow-separation frequency but also the blade-vibration frequency and their scattered modes must be considered. The influence of unsteady flow components with unknown frequencies on stall flutter prediction using the harmonic balance method requires further investigation.

In this study, both the harmonic balance method and time-domain method are employed to perform flutter analysis of blades at large inflow angles. The objective is to investigate how the unknown frequencies of flow separation affect the blade flutter prediction when the harmonic balance method is used and what measures can be taken to tackle the associated issues.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section presents the unsteady flow governing equations and their solution methods.

2.1 Governing Equations

In this study, the unsteady Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes (UFANS) equations are employed for analyzing unsteady flow fields. The Spalart–Allmaras turbulence model is used to obtain eddy viscosity [18]. By integrating the UFANS equations over a control volume using the finite volume scheme, the following semi-discrete equations are obtained

$$V \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + R(Q) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where V denotes the cell volume, Q is the vector of conservative variables, and $R(Q)$ represents the residual vector. For convective flux calculation, the Jameson–Schmidt–Turkel (JST) scheme [19] is employed with spectral-radius-scaled artificial dissipation [20] for suppressing numerical oscillations. The temporal derivative term in Eq. 1 can be dealt with using the time-domain harmonic balance method or a second-order backward differencing together with a dual-time stepping method. The time-domain harmonic balance method is introduced in the next subsection.

2.2 Time-domain Harmonic Balance Method

When the frequency of a temporal periodic flow is known *a priori*, the solution can be effectively resolved by using the time-domain harmonic balance method [17]. The solution variables can be approximated by a truncated Fourier series of the form:

$$Q(t) = \bar{Q} + \sum_{n=1}^N [Q_{A,n} \sin(\omega_n t) + Q_{B,n} \cos(\omega_n t)] \quad (2)$$

where \bar{Q} is the time-averaged value, $Q_{A,n}$ and $Q_{B,n}$ are the Fourier coefficients of the n -th harmonics, ω_n is the n -th angular frequency of an unsteady component, and N is the number of harmonics.

Equation(2) includes $2N + 1$ unknowns. To obtain solutions to these unknowns, $2N + 1$ time instants are selected to form a system of equations. The discrete form of Eq.2 is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{Q}^* \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = [Q(t_1), Q(t_2), \dots, Q(t_{2N+1})]^T$ is the column vector composed of solution variables at $2N + 1$ time instants, $\mathbf{Q}^* = [\bar{Q}, Q_{A,1}, Q_{B,1}, \dots, Q_{A,N}, Q_{B,N}]^T$ is the column vector of Fourier coefficients, and \mathbf{D} is the inverse Fourier transform matrix given by

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_1) & \cos(\omega_1 t_1) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_N t_1) & \cos(\omega_N t_1) \\ 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_2) & \cos(\omega_1 t_2) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_N t_2) & \cos(\omega_N t_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \sin(\omega_1 t_{2N+1}) & \cos(\omega_1 t_{2N+1}) & \cdots & \sin(\omega_N t_{2N+1}) & \cos(\omega_N t_{2N+1}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Following Eq.(2), the time derivative in Eq.(1) can also be represented using a truncated Fourier series

$$\frac{\partial Q(t)}{\partial t} = \sum_{n=1}^N \omega_n [Q_{A,n} \cos(n\omega t) - Q_{B,n} \sin(\omega_n t)] \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the above equation can be written in matrix-vector form as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{Q}^* \quad (6)$$

where matrix \mathbf{D}_t is given by

$$\mathbf{D}_t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \cos(\omega_1 t_1) & -\omega_1 \sin(\omega_1 t_1) & \cdots & \omega_N \cos(\omega_N t_1) & -\omega_N \sin(\omega_N t_1) \\ 0 & \omega_1 \cos(\omega_1 t_2) & -\omega_1 \sin(\omega_1 t_2) & \cdots & \omega_N \cos(\omega_N t_2) & -\omega_N \sin(\omega_N t_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \omega_1 \cos(\omega_1 t_{2N+1}) & -\omega_1 \sin(\omega_1 t_{2N+1}) & \cdots & \omega_N \cos(\omega_N t_{2N+1}) & -\omega_N \sin(\omega_N t_{2N+1}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

By combining Eq.(3) with Eq.(6), the time derivative in Eq.(1) can be further arranged as follows

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}(t)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{Q}^* = \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{D}^{-1} \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{E} \mathbf{Q} \quad (8)$$

In this way, the unsteady equations are transformed into quasi-steady equations at $2N + 1$ discrete time instants. To solve these quasi-steady equations, a time-marching method is adopted, and a pseudo-time derivative term is introduced as follows

$$\mathbf{V} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \tau} + \mathbf{V} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{Q}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where τ is the pseudo-time and $\mathbf{V} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{Q}$ is the time spectral source term.

For unsteady flow with a single fundamental frequency, $2N + 1$ uniformly distributed time instants are sampled over one period. This uniform sampling minimizes the condition number of the inverse Fourier transform matrix \mathbf{D} , thereby ensuring numerical stability. However, when multiple fundamental frequencies are present, the time-sampling strategy must be carefully chosen to avoid ill-conditioning of \mathbf{D} , which may otherwise cause instability in the harmonic balance solution [21]. To address this difficulty, Guédény [22] proposed the Almost Periodic Fourier Transform (APFT) algorithm, which applies the Gram-Schmidt process to improve orthogonality of the basis functions and thereby reduce the condition number of the matrix. The APFT algorithm will be employed later in the flutter analysis with flow separation, which contains multiple frequencies.

3 CASE INTRODUCTION

The Standard Configuration 10 (STCF10) [23] was selected as an example to investigate the flutter at large inflow angles. The blade is obtained by superimposing a modified thickness distribution of the NACA 0006 airfoil on a circular-arc camberline. In our study, the chord length was set to 0.1m, and the pitch-to-chord ratio was set to 1. At the design operating condition, the inlet Mach number is $Ma = 0.7$ and the inflow angle is $\beta = 55^\circ$.

The aerodamping characteristic of the STCF10 cascade with inflow angle in the range of 50° to 60° was investigated by Petrie-Repar [5]. In contrast, the present study extends the investigation to larger inflow angles, specifically from 55° to 70° , to assess the aeroelastic stability in this more challenging operating regime. At the inflow angle of 70° , the flow on the blade's suction surface separates, leading to severe convergence difficulties for both steady and harmonic balance solutions. This provides a case for investigating the influence of flow separation with unknown frequencies on stall flutter analysis using the harmonic balance method.

The inlet of the computational domain was set two chords upstream of the blade leading edge. The outlet of the computational domain was set two chords downstream of the blade trailing edge. A multi-block structured grid was used to discretize the computational domain. The number of grid points is 31,715. Figure 1 shows the computational domain and the mesh.

FIGURE 1: Computational domain and mesh of the STCF10 cascade

At the inlet, a total pressure of 101,325 Pa, a total temperature of 300K, and a flow angle were specified. Four different inlet flow angles of 55°, 60°, 65°, and 70° were investigated. At the outlet, a static pressure of 88,400 Pa were specified.

In the study, a pitch vibration mode was considered. The blade was prescribed to vibrate around the blade mid-chord at a frequency of 181.46Hz for various inlet flow angles. The corresponding reduced frequency based upon the blade chord is $k = 0.5$ when the inflow angle is 55°.

4 SOLVER VERIFICATION

The solver verification consists of two parts. The first part is to verify the solver for steady analysis. The second part is to verify the solver for unsteady analysis due to blade vibration.

For the first part, the results of Petrie-Repar et al. [5] are used as the reference. Note that the reference data were obtained by solving the Euler equations. For a meaningful verification, the Euler equations were also solved in our analysis. Figure 2 presents the comparison of the static pressure coefficient distribution along the axial chord at the design operating point. The differences between the two solutions are negligible.

For the second part, unsteady flow due to a pitch vibration mode at a reduced frequency of $k = 0.5$ was analyzed. The two-dimensional non-reflecting boundary conditions [24] were applied at both the inlet and the outlet to eliminate spurious numerical reflections. The aerodynamic damping at various inter-blade phase angles (IBPAs) was computed at this design operation point, as shown in Figure 3. The aerodynamic dampings are normalized by the value at $IBPA = 180^\circ$. The overall agreement with the reference data is satisfactory. The two peaks and one trough associated with acoustic resonance are well captured. These results clearly verify that the present solver correctly solves the

FIGURE 2: Static pressure coefficient distribution along the axial chord at design operation point for inviscid flow

inviscid flow equations and that the non-reflecting boundary conditions were properly implemented for a time domain harmonic balance analysis.

FIGURE 3: Aerodynamic damping characteristics at design operation point for inviscid flow (pitching mode, reduced frequency $k = 0.5$)

5 First Attempt at Stall Flutter Analysis

To understand the mechanism of stall flutter, the aeroelastic stability of STCF10 at larger inflow angles, namely $\beta = 60^\circ, 65^\circ, 70^\circ$ was investigated. It was found that the viscous effect has a significant influence on the calculated flutter boundaries, particularly at off-design inflow angles [5]. Thus, the

Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes(FANS) equations were solved using the harmonic balance method. The Spalart–Allmaras turbulence model was employed to calculate eddy viscosity [18].

The worksum histories for IBPA=0° at four inflow angles are shown in figure 4. With increasing inflow angle, the worksum progressively increases, corresponding to a reduction in aeroelastic stability. At the inflow angle of 65°, the worksum is close to zero, but still negative. However, at the inflow angle of 70°, the worksum becomes positive, and noticeable oscillations are observed in its convergence history.

FIGURE 4: Worksum histories for a zero IBPA at various inflow angles

The worksum oscillation at the inflow angle of 70° raises three important questions: (i) Is this worksum oscillation linked to flow separation in the field? (ii) Can the average of the oscillating worksum quantify the aeroelastic stability of the blade? (iii) How can a fully converged solution be obtained in a flutter analysis near the stall boundary using the harmonic balance method?

6 Analysis of Flow Separation

To understand the cause of the oscillating worksum at the inflow angle of 70°, steady FANS analysis was performed at the design inflow angle and the inflow angle of 70°. Figure 5 compares the convergence history of the continuity equation residual. The residual at the inflow angle $\beta = 70^\circ$ fails to fully converge. Figure 6 compares the Mach number contours at two inflow angles. In the unconverged steady solution at the inflow angle $\beta = 70^\circ$, the flow separation can be observed on the blade’s suction side. Furthermore, the flow separation is not stationary. It is this flow separation that hinders convergence for both steady and unsteady analysis.

FIGURE 5: Convergence histories of the continuity equation residual of the steady solution at the design inflow angle and a large inflow angle

(a) inflow angle $\beta = 55^\circ$

(b) inflow angle $\beta = 70^\circ$

FIGURE 6: Mach number distribution from steady FANS analysis

To further investigate the flow separation, a time-domain time accurate analysis was performed at the large inflow angle of 70°. The physical time step Δt was set to $10^{-5}s$. A numerical probe was placed near the trailing edge of the blade to record the pressure evolution. Figure 7 presents the time history of the pressure together with its Fourier spectrum. The pressure time history shows a strong periodicity. The FFT analysis reveals a fundamental shedding frequency of approximately $1160Hz$, along with at least three harmonics.

(a) pressure time history

(b) pressure spectrum

FIGURE 7: History of pressure near the trailing edge and its spectrum at the large inflow angle of 70° when the blade is stationary

A series of harmonic balance analyses were also performed at the inflow angle of 70° to investigate how an input frequency would affect solution convergence. The variation of the continuity equation residual of harmonic balance solutions with input frequency is shown in Fig. 8. The results show that full convergence is only achievable when the input frequency is close to 1160Hz . This is also consistent with the observations of Kielb et al. [15].

7 Flutter Analysis with Flow Separation

Based on both the time-domain solution and the harmonic balance solution, the fundamental frequency of flow separation is identified as approximately 1160Hz . The next step is to include the flow separation frequency in a flutter analysis using the harmonic balance method. As the two frequencies are not commensurate with each other, the APFT algorithm was employed to choose the time instants. Figure 9 shows the worksum histories at

(a) residual history

(b) residual vs. frequency

FIGURE 8: The variation of the continuity equation residual of harmonic balance solutions with input frequency

the inflow angle of 70° . The result from a previous analysis without the flow separation frequency is also included in the figure for comparison. Including the flow separation frequency leads to a fully converged worksum. Furthermore, the fully converged worksum is higher than the average of the oscillating worksum. This also implies that the average of the oscillating worksum cannot quantify the blade's aeroelastic stability.

To verify the solution of the harmonic balance method, a time-domain time accurate analysis was performed. The blade was prescribed to vibrate in the same pitching mode with the frequency of 181.46Hz . The physical time step Δt was set to 10^{-5}s . In each time step, the aerodynamic work of the blade was computed, and the history of aerodynamic work is shown in Fig. 10.

The aerodynamic work consists of contributions from both the unsteady flow induced by the blade vibration and the flow separation. The worksum of aeroelastic stability is defined as the work done by the unsteady flow induced by the blade vibra-

FIGURE 9: Worksum histories at a large inflow angle of 70° , obtained using the harmonic balance method with different frequencies

tion over one vibration cycle. To filter out the contribution of flow separation to the worksum, the time integration is carried out over the least common multiple of the vibration-induced unsteady flow period and the flow separation period. Therefore, the worksum was evaluated over 33 blade vibration periods, which correspond to 211 flow separation periods. The resulting worksum is $4.38 \times 10^{-5} J$. While the worksum computed by the harmonic balance method with both the blade frequency and the flow separation frequency is $10.10 \times 10^{-5} J$, which is significantly higher than that obtained from the time domain analysis.

FIGURE 10: History of aerodynamic work for a zero IBPA computed by the time-domain method

Figure 11 compares the distributions of blade surface unsteady pressure amplitudes obtained from the time-domain (TD) solution and the harmonic balance (HB) solution. Specifically, Fig. 11a shows the vibration-induced components, while

Fig. 11b shows those from flow separation. The unsteady pressure amplitudes predicted by the HB method are consistently much larger than those obtained by the TD method, leading to a higher worksum. Referring to reference [25], it is speculated that this overestimated unsteady pressure and worksum are caused by non-physical solutions resulting from scattering modes not being resolved.

(a) blade vibration

(b) flow separation

FIGURE 11: Unsteady flow amplitude of a given frequency component along the axial chord at the large inflow angle of 70° .

To identify the frequency components present in the flow field, a spectral analysis was performed on the time history of the pressure near the trailing edge of the blade (Fig. 12). In comparison with Fig. 7, besides the flow separation frequencies of nf_1 with $n \in [1, 3]$, several additional frequency components appear. First, the smallest frequency is $f_2 \approx 180 Hz$, which is the blade vibration frequency. Second, scattered frequencies of $nf_1 \pm f_2, n \in [1, 3]$ are also observed. These scattered frequencies are generated due to the interaction between the blade vibration unsteady flow and the separation unsteady flow.

(a) pressure signal

(b) FFT analysis

FIGURE 12: History of pressure near the trailing edge of the blade and FFT analysis at the inflow angle of 70° when the blade is vibrating in a pitch mode

The spectral analysis results imply that it is necessary to account for not only the blade vibration frequency and the flow separation frequencies but also their scattering frequencies in a harmonic balance analysis to accurately compute the unsteady flow induced by blade vibrations at the large flow angle. To this end, three different harmonic balance analyses were performed, with their settings presented in Table 1. In HB(N=2), only the blade vibration frequency and the flow separation frequency are included. In HB(N=4), the harmonics of the flow separation frequency of $2f_1$, $3f_1$ are added. Finally, HB(N=10) incorporates all the scattering frequencies of $nf_1 \pm f_2$, $n \in [1, 3]$.

The results of the three harmonic balance analyses and the time-domain time accurate analysis are compared in Figure 13. The unsteady pressure amplitudes induced by blade vibration and flow separation predicted by HB(N=2) and HB(N=4) differ considerably from those of the time-domain solution. This is because these scattering modes are not resolved in those harmonic

TABLE 1: Frequency settings for harmonic balance analysis

Freq. Index	HB(N=2)	HB(N=4)	HB(N=10)
1	f_2	f_2	f_2
2	f_1	f_1	f_1
3		$2f_1$	$2f_1$
4		$3f_1$	$3f_1$
5			$f_1 + f_2$
6			$f_1 - f_2$
7			$2f_1 + f_2$
8			$2f_1 - f_2$
9			$3f_1 + f_2$
10			$3f_1 - f_2$

(a) blade vibration

(b) flow separation

FIGURE 13: Unsteady pressure amplitude distribution along the axial chord at a large inflow angle of 70° .

balance analyses, and their 'energy' is squeezed into those resolved modes, leading to solution contamination. By contrast, when a sufficient number of scattering frequencies are included, as in HB(N=10), the agreement between the harmonic balance solution and the time-domain solution is significantly improved. A large amplitude of unsteady pressure associated with flow separation is observed only at the trailing edge, indicating that the separation predominantly occurs in the region near the trailing edge.

8 Analysis of the Mechanism of Stall Flutter

By incorporating the flow separation frequencies and scattered frequencies into the harmonic balance analysis, the worksum at the large inflow angle of $\beta = 70^\circ$ can be accurately calculated. Figure 14a compares the distribution of worksum along the axial chord at different inflow angles for the case of zero IBPA. The negative half-axis corresponds to the pressure surface, and the positive half-axis corresponds to the suction surface. On the pressure surface, both the negative and positive worksum increase as the inflow angle increases, while the total worksum remains nearly constant. On the suction surface, the positive worksum near the leading edge increases as the inflow angle increases. Meanwhile, the worksum near the trailing edge changes from negative to positive. This positive worksum on the suction surface near the trailing edge at higher inflow angles is likely attributed to flow separation. This ultimately leads to the occurrence of stall flutter.

Figure 14b presents the distribution of near-wall axial velocity along the blade surface. When the near-wall axial velocity is less than zero, flow separation occurs. At inflow angles of $\beta = 55^\circ$ and $\beta = 60^\circ$, the near-wall axial velocity along the blade surface remains positive, indicating no flow separation. When the inflow angle increases to $\beta = 65^\circ$, the near-wall axial velocity near the trailing edge of the suction side becomes negative, revealing the onset of flow separation at about 0.8 chord length on the suction surface. As the inflow angle further increases to $\beta = 70^\circ$, the separation point moves upstream to about 0.4 chord length, and the near-wall axial velocity becomes more negative. By comparing with Fig. 14a, it is evident that the location of flow separation coincides closely with the region where the worksum on the suction surface turns positive. As the separation intensity increases, the positive worksum also intensifies. Therefore, it can be concluded that flow separation leads to a reduction in aeroelastic stability and eventually results in flutter in this cascade.

9 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper presents a flutter analysis of a two-dimensional cascade under near-stall conditions using both the harmonic balance method and the time-domain method. It is found that the presence of unsteady flow components with unknown frequen-

(a) worksum

(b) axial velocity

FIGURE 14: Distribution of the worksum and the near-wall axial velocity along the axial chord at various inflow angles ($-1 < x/c < 0$ is the pressure side and $0 < x/c < 1$ is the suction side)

cies hinders the convergence of harmonic balance solutions. To address this issue, the unsteady frequencies of the flow separation are identified via time-domain simulations and subsequently incorporated into the harmonic balance solution. The results demonstrate that, by including the flow separation frequency, the solution of the harmonic balance equations can achieve convergence. Furthermore, in flutter analysis involving flow separation using the harmonic balance method, it is essential to include scattered frequencies due to the interaction between blade vibration and flow separation. Failure to do that will squeeze the energy of these unresolved flow components into the blade vibration unsteady flow, leading to a contaminated solution. Finally, the

aeroelastic stability is predicted at a series of large inflow angles, which indicates that the flow separation has a destabilizing effect on the blade aeroelasticity.

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